

LEADING PERSONNEL IN THE PERIOD OF NATIONAL RISE
SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL NECESSITY OF DEVELOPING MORAL-
AESTHETIC CULTURE

Inoyatkhan Madimarovna Arzimatova,

Associate Professor of Fergana State University, Candidate of Philosophy,
Uzbekistan, Fergana city

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Abstract: *This article states that the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in today's new stage of development is inextricably linked with the fundamental improvement of the activities in the field of public administration, the development of ethical and aesthetic culture in the leadership staff, and through this, the formation of the opportunity to perform their work efficiency, attitude to social changes and responsibility at a high level, ethical and through the development of aesthetic culture, the issues of improving their honesty and fair functioning skills are highlighted.*

Key words: *reforms, state management bodies, leadership responsibility, moral-aesthetic culture, justice and honesty vaccine, self-criticism, moral norms, leadership spirituality, responsibility, civility.*

РУКОВОДЯЩИЕ КАДРЫ В ПЕРИОД НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ПОДЪЕМА
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ
ПРАВСТВЕННО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

Аннотация: *В данной статье утверждается, что эффективность реформ, реализуемых на сегодняшнем новом этапе развития, неразрывно связана с коренным улучшением деятельности в сфере государственного управления, развитием этической и эстетической культуры у руководящего состава, а через это и формированием возможности выполнять свои эффективность работы, отношение к социальным изменениям и ответственность на высоком уровне, этичность и через развитие эстетической культуры освещаются вопросы повышения их честности и навыков добросовестного функционирования.*

Ключевые слова: *реформы, органы государственного управления, ответственность руководства, нравственно-эстетическая культура, вакцинация против справедливости и честности, самокритика, моральные нормы, духовность руководства, ответственность, вежливость.*

INTRODUCTION

As a result of administrative reforms in the world, various models of evaluating the effectiveness of the state management bodies and the professional and ethical culture of management personnel are being formed. In the modern concepts used to increase the efficiency of management in developed countries, the theoretical approaches to increase the efficiency of public administration, strengthening the responsibility of management personnel, optimization of state bodies and their development stages are revealed. An important result of reforms in the public administration system is to increase efficiency and save budget funds. For this purpose, it is envisaged to develop ethical and aesthetic culture among the leading personnel and through this, to form their work efficiency, their attitude to social changes and the ability to fulfill their responsibilities at a high level. Therefore, it is important to improve the research work on the development of ethical and aesthetic culture of management personnel, the basis of regulatory legal documents, and the expansion of scientific research work in this regard.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In advanced research institutes and international centers of the world, a lot of research work is being carried out on the legal, political, philosophical, sociological and psychological aspects of improving and optimizing the activities of management bodies and leading personnel, carrying out populist management reforms. Within the framework of philosophical sciences, a number of fundamental studies are being carried out on the activities of management personnel, the foundations and development mechanisms of the management system. At the same time, the expansion of corrupt relations in the management system, the popularization of the authoritarian and bureaucratic form of management, the formation of the ethical and aesthetic culture of management personnel and the factors influencing it, the need to expand the research on the priority tasks in this regard is increasing.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, it is clear that the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in our country is inextricably linked with the radical improvement of the activity in the field of public administration. Therefore, on the basis of the fundamental reforms of recent years, many legal bases and several scientific research works are being carried out to improve the activities of state administration, management bodies and leading personnel, to introduce new approaches and to create a management structure focused on the priority of people's interests. After all, "life itself requires us to form a professional, fast and efficient public service system, to open a wide way for new-thinking, enterprising, patriotic personnel" [1]. These requirements make "the task of raising honest and clean personnel who understand the goals and objectives of our reforms, who will sincerely help the implementation of the New Uzbekistan strategy of our people" [2] even more urgent.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Today, one of the urgent tasks is to educate the leading personnel based on the vaccine of justice and honesty. In this regard, a lot of research work is being conducted on personnel training. There is a need for philosophical studies aimed at forming honesty and fair functioning skills in management personnel through the development of ethical and aesthetic culture. The present period - the period of radical change of the civil society in terms of quality, requires from each organization, from each of its members, determined effort, accuracy in evaluating their activities, hard work and self-sacrifice. Special responsibilities are assigned to management personnel. In all their activities, they should demonstrate unity of work, self-criticism, and in general, be an example in following advanced human and moral norms. It is necessary to improve leadership activities, methods and tools in all areas.

Currently, there is a growing tendency to view leadership as a purely professional activity, narrowing it down as an official and a field of official study. In recent years, after long debates, specialists who study the issues of this field are trying to interpret these concepts differently in the form of "an official and a person performing management functions" (*dolzhnostnoe litso i litso, vpolnyayushchee upravlencheskie funktsii*) [3].

To date, a number of works on the selection of leading personnel have been created, and we can note them as works that are directly relevant to the culture of management, and at the same time as scientific-theoretical, practical-educational sources. In these works, the issues of selection of leadership personnel are covered in different ways. Some of them analyze this process in connection with the socio-political, economic and cultural-spiritual development process of the society, while some of them show it as a unique program covering a set of principles related to the selection of leading personnel and selection for leadership. Therefore, according to the approach

to the issue, scientific and theoretical sources can be divided into two groups. The first is direct sources, in which the issues of choosing a leader or being selected for leadership are covered as comprehensively as possible. The second is indirect sources. They include the opinions recorded by different people and different works, and although they essentially express views on leadership, they give more information about the spirituality and moral characteristics of the leader. Examples of artistic creations are mentioned as such sources in most cases.

A leader must manage people, a team, that is, he is distinguished from others by his leadership qualities. He is in front of everyone's eyes in the labor team and society, he solves problems related to work and life, and if necessary, the fate of his subordinates. Therefore, he has more responsibility towards others. In this sense, responsibility is the main criterion in the training of modern managers, and it is necessary to be firm in the fulfillment of this duty. What is the criterion of responsibility in this sense? In general, what is management and what are the leadership skills in it? In this sense, justice is the first condition of management and the responsibility of a modern leader. The criterion of justice is not to separate from the people and satisfy their appeal. Failure to be fair in one's work indicates the lack of responsibility of the leader. Because the injustice of the leader leads to the moral violation of people, the decline of society and the loss of faith in the future. What can happen if the leader violates the criterion of justice while the struggle for building a just society is going on?! For this reason, being just is defined in the holy books as the nature of a person. Calling white white and black black, telling the truth and working with the truth is justice. Thus, the second condition of the leader's responsibility is to be a leader in the literal sense. Leadership is about staying one step ahead of people and being able to see and live with tomorrow's prospects and challenges. This can be called having a strategic objective.

Leadership is a profession, not a set of tasks or a course of action. Therefore, to lead, a person needs the necessary knowledge, skills and competences, skills, professional sophistication, experience, abilities and unique characteristics.

According to research scientists R.J. Ishmukhamedov, A.A. Abdukadirov, A.Kh. Pardaev, the leader:

- reputable, influential and reliable;
- business-minded, capable and pleasant;
- loving and devoted to his work;
- persistent and breaking his word;
- conscientious, caring, honest and self-confident;
- should be well-dressed, middle-aged, elegant and not given to fancy clothes [4].

The high level of spirituality, responsibility and civility, which are important criteria in determining the image of a leader, also plays an important role. This is not only a requirement of the transition period, but also a factor that renews the concept of a manager who can provide the great future of Uzbekistan and is able to serve it.

In the process of building a democratic, legal state and a civil society in the new Uzbekistan, the persons who occupy leadership positions in the system of state and society management, and their spirituality, play an important role. The leader not only participates in the management of the state and society, but also serves as an example to the subordinates, in particular, the subordinate management staff. Therefore, the training of a leader is a matter of great importance. Therefore, it is necessary to start training a leader at the lowest level. Therefore, it is advisable to start work on this at the first stage of education. It was the idea of forming a new generation of leaders along

with bringing up a new generation in general. Therefore, high spirituality and culture are also important in the concept of a leader. This was not only a requirement of the transition period, but also a factor that significantly renewed the concept of a leader who could provide the great future of Uzbekistan and serve it.

DISCUSSION

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the training of modern management personnel requires a scientific approach, taking into account the objective situation. The process of training management personnel in Uzbekistan has a programmatic basis and consists of a continuous system of a number of activities, such as the selection of talented students and youth of Uzbekistan, improving their level of knowledge, and forming their professional skills. At this point, it is necessary to dwell on professional ethics. According to A. Sher, "... it is impolite for a leader to treat subordinates with disdain and rudeness, to look narrowly at the needs and desires of ordinary people in the area or organization entrusted to him, in order to gain personal wealth. Sacrificing the interests of the country, region or organization through corruption is immoral and can be considered as treason not only to the leadership profession, but also to the Motherland. This is why professional etiquette is sometimes called professional ethics.

Thus, specific criteria have been developed in Uzbekistan for the training of modern managers and they are being put into practice. These criteria are consistent with modern management methods and democratic principles of leadership.

Today, we attach great importance to the creation of human resources. Every leader considers it his duty to cultivate the reserve to raise his employee from the bottom to the top. How deeply he feels his duty and task is determined by how carefully he prepares personnel who are able to replace him at a certain time. In order to further improve the experience of the selection of employees, the personnel included in the reserve should feel that their work and abilities are appreciated, that if they work actively and conscientiously, they can hope for the help and support of the higher authority, and they can hope for promotion in the service path.

CONCLUSION

After all, in the new Uzbekistan, the main principles of the personnel policy put forward by the head of state are required to be applied without deviation to the civil society. It is the sacred duty of all of us to clearly and thoroughly implement this requirement into life. In the socio-economic and spiritual development of our republic, meticulous intelligence, leadership with a clear understanding of the work leads to success. Taking care of this should be one of our main and important tasks.

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